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Open Access Bibliometrics: A Decadal Study of Research Output from Puducherry's Medical Colleges with SCILIT Data (2015–2025)

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: The study aimed to assess the usefulness of open-access bibliometric platforms for institutional research evaluation by examining research productivity, citation impact, subject distribution, collaboration patterns, and open-access publishing trends of seven private medical colleges in Puducherry, India, over the period 2015 to 2025.

Methodology: A decadal bibliometric analysis was conducted using data retrieved from the Scilit database. Publications affiliated with the selected medical colleges were identified through affiliation-based searches and manually verified for accuracy. Standard bibliometric indicators, including publication output, citation counts, average citations, subject areas, collaboration types, and open-access status, were analyzed using descriptive statistical techniques.

Findings: The analysis revealed a substantial increase in publication output across all institutions, with notable acceleration after 2020. Despite rising productivity, citation impact remained uneven, with a small proportion of publications accounting for most citations, indicating a skewed distribution. Clinical medicine emerged as the

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dominant subject area, while growing contributions were observed in public health and interdisciplinary research. Open-access publishing increased steadily throughout the study period, reflecting greater emphasis on visibility and compliance with contemporary academic practices. Collaboration patterns showed a strong preference for domestic partnerships, with limited international collaboration.

Implications: *The study demonstrates that Scilit is a viable and accessible tool for monitoring long-term institutional research trends in resource-constrained academic environments. The findings highlight the need for strategic initiatives to improve research quality, expand international collaborations, and align scholarly output with regional and national health priorities to enhance research impact.*

Keywords: Bibliometrics, Open Access, Medical Colleges, Scilit, Research Trends, Puducherry

1. INTRODUCTION

Bibliometric analysis has become an essential approach for assessing research productivity, impact, and collaboration patterns in the biomedical sciences. As global scientific output continues to expand rapidly, systematic evaluations help institutions understand their research trajectories and benchmark performance against national and international standards (Wang et al., 2020; Gupta & Bala, 2011). In India, medical research output has historically been uneven across institutions, with several studies highlighting issues such as low publication volume, quality concerns, and regional disparities in scientific productivity (Ray et al., 2016; Singh, 2020; Nagoba & Davane, 2017). Despite these challenges, recent scientometric investigations show a significant increase in biomedical publications from Indian institutions, shaped by accreditation pressures, faculty promotion requirements, and expanding postgraduate programs (Sachdeva et al., 2017; Muthappan et al., 2024).

Puducherry offers a distinctive academic environment with a cluster of private medical colleges that contribute to a growing share of India's biomedical research. These institutions operate in a competitive landscape shaped by regulatory bodies, institutional goals, and evolving expectations for research visibility. Yet, systematic bibliometric evaluations of private-sector medical colleges in India—particularly within a single geographic region—remain limited. Previous bibliometric studies at national and regional levels have emphasized the need for localized assessments to understand institutional strengths, gaps, and thematic priorities (Mahala & Singh, 2021; Rahaman & Batcha, 2022; Keshri & Tigga, 2020).

At the same time, a shift toward open-access analytics has broadened opportunities for transparent and inclusive research evaluation. Scilit, developed by MDPI, has emerged as a comprehensive open-access database indexing more than 157 million scholarly records through automated harvesting from CrossRef, PubMed, and major publishers (MDPI Blog, 2025). Scilit's expanding use in institutional studies—including work by Ermakov (2024) and Mohammadi et al. (2022)—demonstrates its potential as a cost-free alternative to subscription-based databases such as Scopus and Web of Science. The platform's ability to index a wide

range of outputs, including preprints and book chapters, aligns with recent calls to broaden the scope of scientific impact assessments (Tyagi, 2024; Tyagi, 2025; Lu et al., 2025).

Despite this growing evidence, the private medical education sector in India—especially in regions such as Puducherry—remains underexamined in terms of its research contributions. The seven private medical colleges in Puducherry represent an important and dynamic research ecosystem, yet no decadal bibliometric assessment has systematically evaluated their cumulative scientific output, citation performance, or collaboration networks. Furthermore, understanding their publication patterns can offer insights into institutional strategies, emerging research themes, and alignment with national health priorities.

Therefore, the present study conducts a 10-year bibliometric analysis (2015–2025) using Scilit to evaluate research output from seven private medical colleges in Puducherry. By analyzing publication growth, citation metrics, subject areas, collaboration structures, and open-access trends, this study aims to provide a comprehensive and region-specific understanding of the research landscape. In doing so, it addresses critical gaps in the literature on private-sector medical research performance in India and contributes to the broader discourse on open-access bibliometrics in health sciences.

1.1 Open Bibliometrics and the Choice of SCILIT

Bibliometric evaluation has traditionally depended on subscription-based databases such as Scopus and Web of Science. While these platforms are widely accepted and methodologically robust, their high subscription costs restrict access for many institutions, particularly in resource-constrained academic environments. This limitation has prompted growing interest in open bibliometric platforms that support transparent and reproducible research assessment.

SCILIT, developed by MDPI AG, is a freely accessible scholarly database that aggregates bibliographic metadata from CrossRef, PubMed, and a wide range of academic publishers. Its open structure enables institutional-level searches without financial or technical barriers. In the Indian context, where open-access publishing is increasingly encouraged by regulatory agencies and academic bodies, SCILIT provides practical advantages for tracking research output and visibility.

The decision to use SCILIT as the sole data source in this study was intentional. The study aimed to examine long-term publication trends, collaboration patterns, and open-access growth rather than to conduct citation benchmarking against global elite institutions. SCILIT broad coverage of open-access journals, preprints, and book chapters makes it particularly suitable for capturing the full spectrum of scholarly activity produced by private medical colleges.

At the same time, SCILIT has known limitations. As the database relies on automated metadata harvesting, inconsistencies in author affiliations and delayed citation updates may occur. Unlike curated databases, Scilit does not apply journal quality stratification or standardized subject classification frameworks. These factors can influence citation counts and institutional totals.

Nevertheless, recent institutional scientometric studies have shown that SCILIT yields reliable trend-level insights when supported by careful data cleaning and manual validation.

Given its accessibility, transparency, and relevance to open science monitoring, Scilit was considered an appropriate platform for the present regional and institutional analysis.

1.2 Research Objectives

The objectives of this decadal study (2015–2025) were:

1. To measure the research productivity of the seven medical colleges in Puducherry from 2015 to 2025 using Scilit data.
2. To analyse citation impact and research quality through indicators such as total citations, average citations per publication, and cited-paper ratios.
3. To examine subject-wise research distribution and identify major areas of scientific contribution across institutions.
4. To study collaboration patterns, including international, national, and institutional collaborations.
5. To evaluate the growth of Open Access publishing and its role in increasing visibility and impact.
6. To assess the usefulness of Scilit as an open-access bibliometric tool for institutional research evaluation.

1.3 Limitations

This study has several limitations. Scilit, although comprehensive, may not index all publications uniformly, especially older records or journals with inconsistent metadata. Citation counts in recent years (2023–2025) may be underestimated due to citation delays. Affiliation-based searches can sometimes misclassify authors, leading to potential over- or under-counting of publications. The study relies solely on Scilit and does not compare results with subscription-based databases such as Scopus or Web of Science, which may have different coverage. These limitations should be considered when interpreting the findings.

2. METHODOLOGY AND DATA INTEGRITY

This study examined publications indexed in the Scilit database between January 2015 and June 2025. The analysis covered seven private medical colleges located in Puducherry, India: Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Research Institute (MGMCRI); Sri Manakula Vinayagar Medical College and Hospital (SMVMCH); Pondicherry Institute of Medical Sciences (PIMS); Aarupadai Veedu Medical College and Hospital (AVMC); Indira Gandhi Medical College and Research Institute (IGMCRI); Sri Venkateshwaraa Medical College Hospital and Research Centre (SVMCH&RC); and Vinayaka Missions Medical College (VMMC).

2.1. Data Retrieval and Affiliation Verification

Publication records were retrieved using the institutional affiliation search function in SCILIT. Searches were conducted using official institutional names along with commonly used abbreviations and known variant spellings. To improve data accuracy, retrieved records were exported to Microsoft Excel for manual verification.

Affiliation cleaning was carried out in multiple stages. Duplicate records were removed, and publications with incomplete or ambiguous affiliation information were examined individually.

In cases where affiliations referred to teaching hospitals, trust names, or campus-level units, records were reassigned to the corresponding parent medical college after verifying author details and publisher metadata. This process helped reduce overcounting and misattribution of institutional output

2.3 Bibliometric Indicators and Analysis

Following data cleaning, standard bibliometric indicators were calculated, including total publications, total citations, average citations per publication, and the proportion of cited papers. Open-access status was identified using SCILIT OA tags. Descriptive statistical analysis, trend visualization, and institutional comparisons were performed using Microsoft Excel. After cleaning, the final dataset was used to compute the following bibliometric indicators:

- **Total Publications (TP):** Count of all publication types (articles, book chapters, preprints, conference papers, etc.).
- **Total Citations (TC):** Cumulative citations received by these publications.
- **Average Citations per Publication (ACPP):** $TC \div TP$.
- **Cited Publication Percentage (CPP):** Share of outputs receiving at least one citation.
- **Collaboration Types:** Classified as international, domestic inter-institutional, domestic intra-institutional, or single-authored.
- **Open Access Output:** Publications marked as OA within SCILIT.

3. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Bibliometric and scientometric studies have increasingly been used to assess the growth, impact, and collaborative patterns of research across disciplines and geographic regions. As scholarly communication evolves, open-access platforms such as Scilit have strengthened global research visibility by offering freely accessible metadata and analytics (MDPI Blog, 2025). The utility of Scilit as a research-supporting bibliographic system has been demonstrated in institutional case studies, including analyses of publication metrics from the Kazan Federal University, confirming its accuracy and comprehensive coverage for scientometric evaluations (Ermakov, 2024).

At the global level, bibliometric assessments have mapped research activity across fields such as global health, revealing significant thematic growth, increasing collaboration, and rising visibility of open-access publications (Wang et al., 2020). Similar disciplinary analyses, such as studies of information retrieval in medical sciences (Mohammadi et al., 2022) and occupational therapy research in Scopus (Sau & Nayak, 2023), emphasize how publication volume, citation behavior, and journal selection patterns influence the evolution of a scientific field.

Within India, several studies highlight substantial expansion in biomedical research output. Analyses of national research productivity reveal upward trends across medical specialties (Ray et al., 2016; Singh, 2020), although concerns persist regarding quality, regional disparities, and the prevalence of publications in low-impact journals (Gupta & Bala, 2011; Nagoba & Davane, 2017). Sector-specific reviews, such as those focusing on the Siddha system of medicine (Muthappan et al., 2024), underscore the need for balanced development of both quality and quantity. Further, bibliometric assessments of Indian universities (Mahala & Singh, 2021; Rahaman & Batcha, 2022) and premier management institutions (Tyagi, 2024; Tyagi,

2025) show that publication performance varies widely depending on funding, infrastructure, and disciplinary focus.

Studies of research output from Indian medical students (Sachdeva et al., 2017) and health-resource-constrained states such as Bihar (Keshri & Tigga, 2020) also reveal the influence of institutional support, mentorship, and research culture on publication productivity. More recent analyses highlight increasing global engagement, especially as patient and public involvement research gains prominence in health sciences (Lu et al., 2025). Collectively, these studies illustrate how bibliometric methods can reveal structural strengths, productivity patterns, and capacity gaps in national research ecosystems.

In the Indian context, private medical colleges—the focus of the present study—play an increasingly significant role in national publication output. However, existing literature seldom provides institution-to-institution comparison among private medical schools using open-access bibliometric databases. This gap underscores the relevance of conducting a decadal analysis based on Scilit data to evaluate research activity, citation influence, collaboration maturity, and thematic strengths among Puducherry’s private medical colleges. Findings from such regional analyses can complement national-level scientometric reviews and contribute to evidence-based institutional policy strengthening.

4. RESULTS: RESEARCH PRODUCTIVITY AND GROWTH DYNAMICS

4.1. Annual Growth of Publications

Table 1 and Table 2, visualised in Figure 1, reveal a clear institutional hierarchy in research productivity over the study period. MGMCRI emerged as the most productive institution with 1,775 publications, followed by PIMS (1,034), SMVMCH (682), IGMCRI (488), AVMC (322), SVMCH&RC (311), and VMMC (156). Cumulatively, the seven institutions contributed 4,768 publications to the scholarly record between 2015 and 2025.

Table 1: Institutional Publications and Comparative Growth Index (2015–2024)

Institution	2015 Output	2024 Output	Growth (2015–2024)
MGMCRI	124	251	+102.4%
PIMS	73	118	+61.6%
IGMCRI	39	56	+43.6%
SMVMCH	29	96	+231.0%
AVMC	3	48	+1500.0%
SVMCH&RC	10	50	+400.0%
VMMC	3	16	+433.3%

Year-wise trend analysis (Table 2, Figure 1) reveals a pronounced growth inflection around 2020–2021 across most institutions, coinciding with the COVID-19 period, which is known to have stimulated clinical and medical research output globally. MGMCRI demonstrated the most consistent upward trajectory, rising from 124 publications in 2015 to a decadal peak of 251 in 2024—a growth of 102.4% (Table 1). PIMS showed robust productivity peaking at 123 in 2021 before declining to 59 in 2025, which may reflect faculty transitions or a shift in research prioritisation. Among the smaller institutions, AVMC registered the most dramatic relative growth from just 3 publications in 2015 to 48 in 2024—a 1,500% increase, the highest relative growth rate in the cohort (Table 1). SMVMCH similarly expanded from 29 in 2015 to 105 in 2025 (+231%), while SVMCH&RC and VMMC recorded growth rates of 400% and 433.3% respectively, though their absolute volumes remain comparatively modest.

These trends collectively confirm a sustained and institution-wide upward momentum in research output, particularly in the post-2020 period.

Table 2: Year-wise Publication Counts (2015–2025) by college

Year	MGMCRI	SMVMCH	PIMS	AVMC	IGMCRI	SVMCH&RC	VMC
2015	124	29	73	3	39	10	3
2016	114	23	84	3	34	5	7
2017	137	40	113	15	31	19	9
2018	139	42	100	11	36	27	12
2019	166	59	103	24	39	34	15
2020	160	56	74	27	32	31	25
2021	173	87	123	32	57	32	23
2022	187	67	102	56	50	41	21
2023	164	78	85	54	68	34	14
2024	251	96	118	48	56	50	16
2025	160	105	59	49	46	28	11

Figure 1: Annual Publication Trends by Institution (2015–2025)

4.2. Distribution of Publication Types

As shown in Table 3 and Figure 2, journal articles overwhelmingly dominate scholarly output, accounting for 4,510 of the total 4,768 records (94.6%). This predominance reflects the well-established preference for peer-reviewed journal publications within Indian medical academia, where such outputs carry significant weight in accreditation and faculty promotion criteria. Book chapters constitute the second-largest category with 120 items (2.5%), followed by preprints (78; 1.6%), proceedings articles (25; 0.5%), and other output types (35; 0.7%). The presence of preprints, while modest, signals an emerging awareness of open scholarly communication practices among faculty. Institutions such as MGMCRI and PIMS, which lead in overall publication volume, also contribute the majority of non-article outputs, reflecting a greater degree of research diversification and broader engagement with scholarly dissemination channels beyond conventional journal publication.

Table 3: Distribution of Publication Types (2015–2025)

Publication Type	Count
Journal-Article	4510
Book-Chapter	120
Preprint	78
Proceedings-Article	25
Others	35

Figure 2: Distribution of Scholarly Output by Publication Type

4.3. Citation Impact and Quality Metrics

PIMS leads in Average Citations per Publication (ACPP = 8.84) with 9,138 total citations; MGMCRI has the highest total citations (9,229) but a lower ACPP (5.20). IGMCRI also performs strongly (ACPP = 7.04). Overall annual citations increased from 183 in 2015 to 1,518 in 2024, but median citation counts remain low (Q2 = 0–1), demonstrating a long-tail distribution where a small fraction of papers drive average citation performance which are mentioned in Table 4 & Figure 3.

Table 4: Core Bibliometric Metrics and Citation Distribution (2015–2025)

Institution	Total Publications	Total Citations	ACPP	Cited Pubs %	Self-Cite %	Q1	Median (Q2)	Q3
MGMCRI	1775	9229	5.2	63.5%	1.8%	N/A	0/1	N/A
SMVMCH	682	2509	3.68	53.8%	1.9%	0	1	4
PIMS	1034	9138	8.84	74.3%	1.6%	0	1	6
AVMC	322	1048	3.25	54.7%	2.2%	0	1	4
IGMCRI	488	3436	7.04	69.7%	0.6%	0	1.3	6
SVMCH&RC	311	1121	3.6	49.5%	0.4%	0	0	3
VMMC	156	483	3.1	56.4%	0.8%	0	1	3

Figure 3: Total Cumulative Citations by Institution (2015–2025)

4.4. Open Access Publication Trends

Figure 4 depicts the annual growth trajectory of Open Access (OA) publications from 2015 to 2025 across the seven institutions collectively. OA output grew from 188 publications in 2015 to a decadal peak of 434 in 2024, representing a cumulative increase of 130.9%. The trend, while broadly upward, was not linear: a notable interim peak of 279 was observed in 2019, followed by a temporary decline to 210 in both 2020 and 2021—likely attributable to pandemic-related disruptions in institutional research activity and journal processing. OA output then resumed a sharp upward trajectory through 2022 (254) and 2023 (324) before reaching its peak in 2024 (434). The marginal decline to 308 in 2025 may reflect the partial nature of the 2025 dataset given the mid-year data retrieval window. Overall, the sustained growth in OA publishing aligns with increasing institutional compliance with open science mandates promoted by national regulatory bodies, as well as the expanding availability of affordable and fee-waived OA journals indexed within Scilit. The upward OA trend also correlates broadly with the general rise in total publications observed in Figure 1, suggesting that OA publishing has become a normalised rather than exceptional mode of dissemination across the cohort.

Figure 4: Annual Open Access Publication Trend (2015–2025)

4.5. Collaboration and Authorship Networks

Table 5 and Figure 5 reveal the collaboration architecture of the seven institutions over the study period. Domestic intra-organisational collaboration—publications involving co-authors from within the same institution—is the dominant mode across all colleges, averaging 53.7% of total output. This is followed by domestic inter-organisational collaboration (average 33.5%), reflecting a degree of partnership with other Indian institutions. International collaboration remains the least developed dimension, averaging only 8.3% across the cohort. At the institutional level, AVMC records the highest international collaboration rate (16.8%), followed by PIMS (10.3%) and IGMCRI (8.2%), while VMMC (3.8%), SMVMCH (4.3%), and SVMCH&RC (4.5%) demonstrate minimal cross-border research engagement (Table 5). Single-authored publications remain rare, averaging below 8.6% across all institutions, which is consistent with the inherently team-based nature of clinical medical research and the multi-disciplinary demands of hospital-based studies.

The predominance of intra-institutional collaboration, as illustrated in Figure 5, may indicate a degree of research insularity that could limit methodological diversity, access to

specialist expertise, and citation reach. In contrast, studies characterised by inter-institutional or international collaboration are consistently associated with higher citation rates in the bibliometric literature. Broadening research partnerships—through collaborative grant applications, joint postgraduate supervision, and inter-institutional clinical trials—represents a strategic priority for enhancing the scholarly visibility and global impact of Puducherry’s private medical sector.

Table 5: Collaboration Patterns (2015–2025)

Institution	International %	Domestic Inter-org %	Domestic Intra-org %	Single Authorship %
MGMCRI	6.3%	24.1%	56.9%	12.7%
SMVMCH	4.3%	28.2%	62.2%	5.4%
PIMS	10.3%	34.1%	45.8%	9.7%
AVMC	16.8%	31.7%	45.0%	6.5%
IGMCRI	8.2%	42.8%	42.6%	6.4%
SVMCH&RC	4.5%	31.8%	58.2%	5.5%
VMMC	3.8%	39.1%	53.8%	3.2%

Figure 5: Collaboration Patterns by Type (Average % across all 7 colleges)

4.6. Publishing Ecosystem: Preferred Journals and Publishers

The publishing ecosystem analysis presented in Table 6 reveals the preferred journal outlets of the seven institutions. Across the cohort, the Journal of Clinical and Diagnostic Research, Cureus, the International Journal of Reproduction, Contraception, Obstetrics and Gynecology, and the Indian Journal of Anaesthesia emerge as the most frequently used publication venues. The high frequency of Cureus publications an open-access, peer-reviewed journal with a streamlined publication model—is consistent with the broader OA growth trend documented in Figure 4. Institutional specialisation is also evident: SMVMCH shows a concentration in dermatology journals, PIMS and MGMCRI demonstrate strong engagement with otolaryngology and general medicine outlets, while AVMC’s output is concentrated in paediatric and surgical journals (Table 6). This subject-specific clustering reflects each institution’s departmental strengths and clinical service profile.

Table 7 identifies the major citing publishers across all seven institutions. Springer Nature consistently ranks first as the leading citing publisher—accounting for citation counts ranging from 105 (VMMC) to 1,811 (PIMS)—followed by Elsevier, Medknow, Wiley, and MDPI AG. The dominance of Springer Nature and Elsevier as citing publishers confirms that the research produced by Puducherry’s private medical colleges is being integrated into

mainstream international scholarship, even where institutions primarily publish in regional or open-access journals. The strong presence of MDPI AG as a citing publisher further reinforces the growing reciprocal engagement between Scilit-indexed open-access publications and the broader biomedical research literature. Medknow's consistent appearance across institutions reflects the significant role of Indian journal publishing ecosystems in mediating regional citation flows.

Table 6: Top Source Titles by Publication Count - Per Institution

Rank	MGMCRI	SMVMCH	PIMS	AVMC	IGMCRI	SVMCH&RC	VMMC
1	Journal of Clinical and Diagnostic Research (111)	Indian Dermatology Online Journal (38)	Journal of Current Research in Scientific Medicine (88)	Indian Journal of Pediatrics (17)	Cureus (32)	International Journal Of Reproduction... (27)	International Journal Of Reproduction... (11)
2	Cureus (71)	Global Journal of Health Sciences and Research (31)	Cureus (29)	International Journal of Otorhinolaryngology and Head and Neck Surgery (12)	Journal of Clinical and Diagnostic Research (21)	International Journal Of Community Medicine And Public Health (14)	International Journal Of Community Medicine And Public Health (14)
3	International Journal of Reproduction... (42)	Journal of Family Medicine and Primary Care (22)	International Journal Of Community Medicine And Public Health (28)	International Surgery Journal (11)	Indian Journal of Anaesthesia (18)	Cureus (13)	Revista Brasileira de Ortopedia (5)
4	Indian Journal of Anaesthesia (39)	Journal of Clinical and Diagnostic Research (20)	Journal of Clinical and Diagnostic Research (23)	International Journal of Contemporary Pediatrics (10)	Journal of Family Medicine and Primary Care (13)	International Journal Of Contemporary Pediatrics (11)	Indian Journal of Medical Specialties (4)
5	International Journal of Advances in Medicine (38)	Indian Journal of Dermatology, Venereology and Leprology (17)	Indian Journal of Otolaryngology and Head & Neck Surgery (18)	Plastic and Reconstructive Surgery - Global Open (10)	International Journal Of Community Medicine And Public Health (12)	International Journal of Medical Research & Review (7)	International Journal Of Community Medicine And Public Health (4)
6	International Surgery Journal (33)	Cureus (16)	Indian Journal of Endocrinology and	International Journal of Advances in Medicine (9)	International Journal Of Reproduction... (12)	International Journal of Otorhinolaryngology... (7)	Journal of Family Medicine and

			Metabolism (15)				Primary Care (4?)
7	International Journal Of Community Medicine And Public Health (30)	Clinical and Experimental Dermatology (14)	Indian Journal Of Psychological Medicine (15)	International Journal Of Community Medicine And Public Health (9)	Anesthesia: Essays and Researches (11)	Journal of Family Medicine and Primary Care (7)	Annals of Indian Academy of Neurology (3)
8	Indian Journal Of Ophthalmology (25)	Indian Journal of Community Medicine (13)	International Journal of Research in Medical Sciences (14)	International Journal of Research in Dermatology (6)	Asian Journal of Medical Sciences (11)	Asian Journal of Medical Sciences (6)	Epidemiology International (2)
9	Indian Journal of Otolaryngology... (23)	International Journal Of Contemporary Pediatrics (13)	Indian Journal of Clinical and Experimental Ophthalmology (12)	Alcoholism Treatment Quarterly (4)	International Journal Of Contemporary Pediatrics (9)	BMJ Case Reports (6)	Anaesthesia, Pain & Intensive Care (2)
10	Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research (21)	The American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene (13)	Indian Journal of Community Medicine (12)	IP International Journal of Medical Paediatrics and Oncology (4)	Indian Pediatrics (7)	Clinical Dermatology Review (5)	IAR Journal of Medicine and Surgery Research (2)

The Table 6 listing top 10 journals by institution is included in the supplementary file. Representative high-frequency journals include Journal of Clinical and Diagnostic Research; Cureus; International Journal of Reproduction, Contraception, Obstetrics and Gynecology; Indian Journal of Anaesthesia; and International Journal of Advances in Medicine.

Table 7: Top Citing Publishers by Citation Count - Per Institution

Ran k	MGMCRI	SMVMCH	PIMS	AVMC	IGMCRI	SVMCH&R C	VMMC
1	Springer Nature (1783)	Springer Nature (532)	Springer Nature (1811)	Springer Nature (216)	Springer Nature (703)	Springer Nature (209)	Springer Nature (105)
2	Elsevier (1396)	Medknow (283)	Elsevier (1342)	Elsevier (142)	Elsevier (448)	Elsevier (154)	Elsevier (81)
3	MDPI AG (646)	Elsevier (275)	Medknow (671)	MDPI AG (88)	Medknow (318)	MDPI AG (92)	MDPI AG (39)
4	Wiley (593)	Wiley (153)	Wiley (521)	Wiley (76)	Wiley (184)	Medknow (70)	Wiley (32)
5	Medknow (584)	MDPI AG (128)	MDPI AG (498)	Frontiers Media SA (52)	MDPI AG (177)	Wiley (61)	Wolters Kluwer Health (24)
6	Frontiers Media SA (380)	Wolters Kluwer Health (118)	Wolters Kluwer Health (377)	Wolters Kluwer Health (43)	Wolters Kluwer Health (157)	Taylor & Francis (54)	Taylor & Francis (10)

7	Wolters Kluwer Health (372)	Taylor & Francis (75)	Taylor & Francis (328)	Medknow (41)	Taylor & Francis (138)	Wolters Kluwer Health (52)	Medknow (19)
8	Taylor & Francis (362)	Scientific Scholar (68)	Frontiers Media SA (309)	Taylor & Francis (35)	PLoS (97)	Frontiers Media SA (40)	SAGE Publications (15)
9	SAGE Publications (224)	Frontiers Media SA (60)	PLoS (228)	Georg Thieme Verlag KG (17)	SAGE Publications (89)	SAGE Publications (26)	Taylor & Francis (10?)
10	PLoS (133)	SAGE Publications (58)	SAGE Publications (228)	SAGE Publications (16)	Frontiers Media SA (77)	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (19)	Jaypee Brothers Medical Publishing (9)

As shown in Table 7 the major citing publishers across all institutions are led by Springer Nature and Elsevier, followed by MDPI, Wiley, and Medknow.

5. DISCUSSION: INSTITUTIONAL TRAJECTORIES AND POLICY CONTEXT

This study examined research productivity across seven private medical colleges in Puducherry over a ten-year period. The overall trend shows a steady rise in scholarly output, with some institutions displaying rapid progress after 2020. This increase is likely driven by accreditation requirements, institutional emphasis on faculty research, and expanding postgraduate programmes that encourage more academic activity.

Despite the growth in publication numbers, the citation impact remains uneven. A small proportion of articles accounts for most citations, while a substantial volume of publications receives minimal attention. This indicates that research visibility and methodological quality need further strengthening. Encouraging publication in reputable journals, improving research design, and fostering stronger scientific writing practices may enhance citation performance.

Collaboration patterns also show a predominantly internal focus. Most publications originate from within the same institution, with limited external or international collaboration. Expanding partnerships can expose faculty to diverse expertise, improve research quality, and increase national and global visibility. Collaborative studies often attract higher citations, and building such networks is especially important for private institutions seeking academic recognition.

The subject-area distribution highlights a strong focus on core clinical specialties, which reflects the teaching and service priorities of private medical colleges. At the same time, growing research activity in public health, infectious diseases, and patient-care themes suggests a gradual shift toward broader health system concerns. Supporting interdisciplinary research may help institutions diversify their contributions and address emerging healthcare challenges.

Overall, the study shows that private medical colleges in Puducherry are increasingly contributing to the academic landscape. However, sustained progress will require continued investment in research training, supportive institutional systems, and a focus on quality alongside quantity.

6. CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that private medical colleges in Puducherry have made significant progress in research productivity over the past decade, with notable increases in publication output and diversification of scholarly contributions. However, the analysis also highlights persistent gaps between quantity and impact, emphasizing the need for improved research quality, stronger collaboration networks, and greater strategic focus on high-priority health areas.

By adopting targeted quality-oriented strategies, strengthening partnerships, and fostering a culture of rigorous scientific inquiry, these institutions can enhance both their academic standing and their contribution to healthcare research in India. The findings also reinforce the value of Scilit as an accessible tool for monitoring institutional research performance and supporting evidence-based academic planning.

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